

submergence stress (increased growth and significantly higher grain yield) (Table 2). Older seedlings tolerated

intermediate submergence better than did younger seedlings. Semidwarf variety CR1018 performed

better than improved tall variety Tilakkachari, which grows locally under submergence. □

Soil fertility and fertilizer management

Effect of continuous application of ammonium sulfate and urea on irrigated rice

A. Buntan and I. T. Corpuz, Agronomy Department, Maros Research Institute for Food Crops, P.O. Box 173, Ujung Pandang, Indonesia

We studied the effect of continuous application of ammonium sulfate on rice yield and on some physicochemical properties of wetland soil.

The clayey soil had pH 6.2 (slightly acidic); 0.12% total N (low); 150 ppm available P (fairly high); 19.8, 7.9, 0.8 meq Ca, Mg, K/100 g soil (high); and 8

ppm $\text{SO}_4\text{-S}$ content (low). N was deficient and S was below the critical 9 ppm level.

The experiment was established in 1984 wet season (WS) after a simple trial to identify the problem of plant yellowing despite the application of urea. The rice crop was observed to respond to the application of ammonium sulfate.

Twelve treatments were arranged in a randomized complete block design with 4 replications (see table). P as TSP and K as KCl were applied (60 kg each) in treatments 2 to 12.

Grain yield was higher when S was applied, at any level. The significant increase in yield was due to N.

Effect of S on grain yield (14% moisture) of IR54. Ujung Pandang, Indonesia, 1984 wet season.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)
Control	2.7
20 kg S/ha as ammonium sulfate	3.9
0 S, 20 kg N/ha as urea	3.7
40 kg S/ha	4.4
0 S, 40 kg N/ha	4.3
60 kg S/ha	4.8
0 S, 60 kg N/ha	4.4
80 kg S/ha	4.4
0 S, 80 kg N/ha	4.2
100 kg S/ha	4.6
0 S, 100 kg N/ha	4.3
0 S, 0 N, 26.4 kg P, 49.8 kg K/ha	3.0
LSD (0.05)	0.6
(0.01)	0.8
CV (%)	11.8

Application of P and K without S or N did not have any significant effect on yield. □

Reaction of IR20 rice to carbofuran and urea

M. A. Salam, Kerala Agricultural University, Cropping System Research Centre, Karamana, Trivandrum 695002, Kerala, India

The reaction of IR20 rice to combinations of carbofuran and urea was studied at Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU) in summer (Feb-Jun) 1983. The objective was to examine the phytotonic effects of carbofuran and its interaction with N.

The experiment was laid out in a factorial combination of three levels of N (0, 60, and 90 kg N/ha as urea) and four levels of carbofuran (0, 1.0, 2.0, and 3.0 kg ai/ha) in a randomized block design with four replications.

Soil at TNAU (11° N, 77° E, and 427 m above mean sea level) was a Vertisol (clay loam) containing 1.0% organic C, 99-8.0-254 ppm available NPK, 0.7 ppm DTPA-extractable Zn, with pH 8.2 and

Influence of carbofuran (0, 1, 2, 3 kg ai/ha) and N on grain yield of IR20. TNAU, Coimbatore, India, 1983.

N (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)				
	No carbofuran	1 kg	2 kg	3 kg	Mean
0	1.9	2.7	2.9	2.9	2.7
60	3.3	3.8	3.1	2.7	3.3
90	4.2	5.0	3.8	4.1	4.2
Mean	3.2	3.8	3.3	3.2	

	LSD (0.05)
Nitrogen (N)	0.5
Carbofuran (C)	0.9
N×C	1.4

EC 0.3 dS/m. The crop was uniformly fertilized and kept insect free by spraying all plots with phosphamidon on a need basis, including plots treated with insecticide.

Carbofuran was incorporated at planting to ensure minimum loss. N as urea was applied in three splits: 50% basal, 25% at tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation.

Tiller production, leaf area index,

root production, and grain yield increased with urea application up to 90 kg N/ha and with carbofuran application up to 1.0 kg ai/ha (see table).

Based on costs, the combination 90 kg N/ha and 1.0 kg ai carbofuran/ha was optimum. Costs were \$2.5/kg carbofuran 3% granule, \$0.5/kg N, \$0.2/kg rough rice, and \$2.91 person (for labor). □